

Advancing Watershed-Scale Hydrodynamic Modeling: Techniques for Comparative Analysis of Saint-Venant Solvers

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Objective

This technical report presents the methodological foundation and supplementary analyses associated with a study evaluating the performance of a newly developed Saint-Venant Equation (SVE) solver, SWMM5+, in comparison with two existing hydraulic models: the U.S. EPA Storm Water Management Model (EPA SWMM) and the Simulation Program for River NeTworks (SPRNT). The comparative modeling framework, introduced in the accompanying journal article titled “Advancing Watershed-Scale Hydrodynamic Modeling with the Saint-Venant Equations”, is applied to regional-scale river networks to assess numerical behavior, solution stability, and hydrodynamic accuracy across different solver architectures. This report provides additional technical documentation, implementation details, and supplemental figures that support the findings and discussions presented in the main manuscript.

In this study, SWMM5+ is validated through model-to-model comparison rather than direct comparison with observational data, due to the substantial challenges inherent in validating large-scale river network models. Observational flow and stage data are often spatially sparse, temporally inconsistent, and subject to measurement uncertainties, which complicate the assessment of how model errors emerge and propagate throughout the system. Additionally, river bathymetric data—crucial for solving the Saint-Venant Equations—are frequently incomplete or of uncertain accuracy across large domains, making it difficult to isolate algorithmic performance from boundary condition uncertainties. Compounding these challenges is the presence of hydraulic infrastructure, such as dams and weirs, whose operational rules are often proprietary or undocumented. These unmodeled anthropogenic controls can significantly influence flow and stage observations, thereby obscuring the attribution of model-observation discrepancies (Turner, Steyaert, Condon, & Voisin, 2021). Consequently, validation in such settings tends to reflect the degree of parameter calibration rather than the intrinsic accuracy of the numerical schemes. Model-to-model comparison thus provides a more transparent means of evaluating the performance of numerical solvers, independent of the confounding effects of observational and structural uncertainties.

In contrast to traditional model-observation comparisons, model-to-model comparison provides a consistent and system-wide framework for evaluating numerical accuracy and stability under identical forcing conditions, boundary specifications, and parameter settings. This approach allows performance to be assessed across a wide spatial domain, overcoming the limitations associated with sparse observational data. Furthermore, it enables detailed examination of hydrodynamic behaviors—such as wave attenuation, numerical dissipation, and solver stability—across complex, watershed-scale networks. By isolating the effects of numerical architecture, model-to-model comparison offers critical insights into the strengths and limitations of each solver, independent of calibration artifacts or observational uncertainties.

This technical documentation outlines the methodological components that support such model inter-comparison studies and may serve as a reference for similar evaluations. The key topics covered include:

1. Development of regional-scale river network models using publicly available datasets.
2. Criteria and procedures for evaluating SWMM5+ suitability for model-to-model comparison.
3. Initialization procedures for Saint-Venant Equation (SVE) simulations, including model spin-up requirements.

4. Post-processing workflows designed to enable robust comparison of spatially and temporally distributed results.
5. Presentation of supplemental simulation results from the SVE-based models.
6. Solver adjustments and configuration settings applied to ensure fair and interpretable comparisons across models.

1 Creation of river network models

1.1 Regional-scale River Basins

The regional-scale river basins examined in the main journal article are the Lavaca and San Jacinto River basins, both located within the Texas-Gulf hydrologic region. The Lavaca River originates in central Texas and drains an area of approximately $5,900 \text{ km}^2$ before discharging into Lavaca Bay. The full river network consists of 3,049 km of channel reaches; however, to streamline the model while preserving hydrodynamic fidelity, first-order tributaries—which have negligible influence on the overall flow dynamics—are represented as nodal inflows rather than explicitly modeled channels. This simplification reduces the effective modeled channel length to 1,291 km. The Lavaca River basin features a relatively mild topographic gradient, with elevations ranging from 0 to 23 m above sea level. Natural channel slopes fall between 0.0001 and 0.002, with an average slope of approximately 0.0003. The network structure and topological configuration of the Lavaca River are illustrated in Figure 1(a).

In contrast, the San Jacinto River—which drains an area of approximately $4,600 \text{ km}^2$, exhibits a more complex branching topology and greater vulnerability to extreme flood events, as evidenced during Hurricane Harvey in 2017. Applying the same channel filtering methodology as used for the Lavaca River, the total modeled channel length is reduced to 1,716 km after excluding first-order tributaries with limited hydraulic influence. Located within the East Texas Plain, the San Jacinto River basin spans elevations from 0 to 120 m above sea level. Excluding localized slope disruptions caused by hydraulic structures, the natural channel slope ranges from 0.0001 to 0.009, with an average slope of 0.00045. The structure and topological configuration of the river network are depicted in Figure 1(b).

Fig. 1. The two selected river networks within the Texas-Gulf region in this study. (a) Lavaca River, (b) San Jacinto River. The blue flowlines are extracted from the NHDPlus dataset (USGS, 2020). Gold stars (1) and (2) are hydrograph locations in Fig. 5; gold stars (3) and (4) are hydrograph locations in Fig. 7.

1.2 From Raw Data to SPRNT

One-dimensional hydrological models for the Lavaca and San Jacinto Rivers were derived from the USGS National Hydrography Dataset (NHDplus) flowlines for Hydrological Unit Code 12 (USGS, 2020). Definition of channel geometry and roughness followed the approach used in the National Water Model (NWM), which defines trapezoidal cross-sections with constant side-wall slope of 0.5 and a bottom width that depends on the Strahler’s stream order of the reach (David et al., 2011; NOAA, 2016). The bottom width ranges between 7 *m* and 40 *m*. The roughness from NWM (Strickler-Manning, *n*) ranges from 0.045 to 0.06. Subcritical flow at the downstream boundary is ensured by fixing the water depth (*H*) to 3 *m*. Hydrological flows throughout the river basins were extracted from the NWM archive and introduced as time-varying nodal boundary conditions (NOAA, 2016). Following the approach by Falter et al. (2016) and Paiva, Collischonn, Bonnet, and de Gonçalves (2012), first order and minor streams (i.e. reaches that are dry a preponderance of the simulation time) were removed. Flow contributions from the excised reaches, when they occur, are incorporated into the hydrological inflows at neighboring nodal boundary conditions. Other network refinement steps were taken, including the omission of 86 “braided” channel reaches, as well as the replacement of 106 reservoirs/dams with simple channels. Such features should be handled by sophisticated river-routing software attempting to make real world predictions. However, for our present scope of comparing different models’ numerical methods for identical simulation parameters, the additional complexity contributed by braided channels or dam-gate operations is not warranted.

Generally, favorable behavior from hydraulic models can be expected when channel segments are of roughly equal length. From the NHDplus dataset, the average river reach length for our test case was 3.1 *km*, with a maximum of 68 *km* and a minimum of 1 *m*. The river systems herein were refined such that each river channel segment was ~ 150 *m* by subdividing longer segments and lengthening shorter ones. Table 1 contains details about the discretization of the Lavaca and San Jacinto NHDplus networks into the NWM form.

Table 1. Topological information of major river networks, excluding first-order reaches, in the Texas-Gulf watershed (Yu et al., 2021).

Network Name	Channel Length (km)	NHDPlus Flowlines	Computational Nodes	Inflow Boundaries
Lavaca	1291	360	6973	67
San Jacinto	1732	690	9659	116

The Lavaca and San Jacinto River network models were originally built as input files for the Simulation Program for River NeTworks (SPRNT). As SPRNT files, these systems were used by Yu, Liu, and Hodges (2017) to study consistent initial conditions for the Saint-Venant equations in river network modeling, by Yu et al. (2021) to evaluate a new method for detecting instability-causing geometry transitions.

1.3 From SPRNT to SWMM

The SPRNT modeling architecture varies from the EPA SWMM modeling architecture in critical ways. To enable a coherent comparison of the results between the modeling paradigms, the models, originally constructed in the SPRNT architecture, must be converted into the EPA SWMM architecture. Fortunately, the SWMM5+ model also used the EPA SWMM architecture, so the Lavaca and San Jacinto models only need to be converted once.

All SVE solvers rely on the same physical parameters, e.g., elevation gradients, cross-section geometry, etc., but how these parameters are handled can vary between modeling environments. Converting from one modeling environment to another is an exercise in finding the analogous data structures for each parameter. Some SPRNT objects, such as “segments”, are directly analogous to SWMM “conduits”; properties like length and upstream/downstream connections are simply copied from SPRNT into the SWMM format. Other network objects require data structure transformation. An example of a network object requiring transformation are multi-nodal junctions in SPRNT being collapsed into single node junctions in the SWMM paradigm (shown with a red Δ in Fig. 2). In SPRNT, a “junction” consists of multiple “nodes” in a complex, where each node can only have one or two connections. Whereas, in SWMM, any node with one or more connections is considered a junction. Merging junctions from SPRNT into SWMM involves the replacement of SPRNT junction complexes with SWMM junction nodes (illustrated in Fig. 3, below). Other network object parameters (e.g. channel geometry, internal boundary conditions, etc.) are simply stored in different data structures between SPRNT and SWMM. The transformation from SPRNT-compatible input files to SWMM-compatible input files, conserves network topology, geometry, and forcing data (i.e. the network information in Table 1 is preserved).

Fig. 2. Schematic showing the data structure shuffling needed to convert from SPRNT-format to SWMM-format. Note the changes in network object jargon between SPRNT and SWMM. Red Δ indicates Junction complex further illustrated in Fig. 3

Fig. 3. Example schematic of “Junction” complex for SPRNT, SWMM5+, and EPA SWMM. State variables like flow (Q) and head (h) are reported as attributes of different network objects depending on the modeling framework.

The SWMM5+ model further transforms the conduit-node EPA SWMM input file into a finite-volume network of elements and faces, while still preserving the network properties. For additional information

about the discretization approach used by SWMM5+, please see Hodges et al. (2024).

2 Evaluation of SWMM5+

In the study, river network simulation results from multiple SVE solvers are compared to assess the effects of program architecture on flood wave peak timing and other hydrodynamic factors. The SPRNT program was expressly designed for river network simulation (Liu, 2014), while previous studies have established EPA SWMM as a suitable model for some river routing simulation (Niazi et al., 2020; Swathi, Raju, & Varma, 2020; Xiong & Melching, 2005). The SWMM5+ program, the newest of these SVE-solver models, was designed as an under-the-hood, parallelized, mass-conservative version of EPA SWMM5 (Hodges et al., 2024). However, SWMM5+ has not been explicitly tested on a regional-scale river network prior to its use herein. This section briefly describes some relevant architectural details about SWMM5+, then compares simulation results to observed data at two locations within the Lavaca river basin.

2.1 Parallelization

The parallelization strategy in SWMM5+ adopts the single program, multiple data (SPMD) approach. Unlike implicit methods commonly used in SVE solvers, which typically require matrix decomposition, the explicit numerical scheme in SWMM5+ enables direct subdivision and distribution of the computational domain across multiple processors. The network subdivision algorithm from Tiernan and Hodges (2022) is adapted to optimize load balancing across processors. Instead of conventional multiprocessing libraries (e.g., OpenMP), SWMM5+ employs Coarray Fortran for parallelization (Hodges et al., 2021). Although the primary focus of this study is not on parallel computation, we include this information to highlight that SWMM5+ supports efficient parallelization, demonstrating its capability to handle large-scale simulations.

2.2 Numerical Method

The numerical framework of SWMM5+ employs an explicit second-order Runge-Kutta (RK2) time-marching scheme to compute flow rate (Q) and volume (V) within finite-volume elements. While the RK2 algorithm exhibits higher temporal discretization discrepancies compared to higher-order time-marching methods, its structure is particularly well-suited for parallel computing architectures. To reduce numerical dependency between adjacent computational elements, SWMM5+ implements a no-neighbor discretization approach within the RK2 scheme (Hodges & Liu, 2019), effectively minimizing communication bandwidth requirements during parallel computation. The time-space discretization structure of the RK2 algorithm is depicted in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. The upper panel illustrates the domain of dependency for an RK2 time advancement in a finite-volume scheme with third-order upwind face reconstruction, while the lower panel depicts a no-neighbor compliant scheme with second-order face reconstruction. The thicker arrows in the upper panel highlight the increased spatial dependency introduced by the third-order scheme. Figure adapted from (Hodges & Liu, 2019).

As illustrated in Figure 4, the finite-volume element faces are reconstructed dynamically during time integration. Traditional approaches typically rely on a combination of upwind and downwind element values for face reconstruction. In contrast, the no-neighbor method implemented in SWMM5+ ensures that reconstructed faces utilize only adjacent elements, thereby minimizing spatial dependency and reducing communication overhead between processors. This design significantly decreases data exchange between computational cores, improving the efficiency of parallel computation. A detailed explanation can be found in (Hodges & Liu, 2019).

The numerical stability of the RK2 scheme is governed by the CFL condition, which necessitates that $u\Delta t/\Delta x \leq C_{max}$ to prevent numerical divergence. In SWMM5+, however, to ensure global numerical stability, the CFL constraint is further restricted to $CFL < \sqrt{2}/2$, with a dynamically adjusted time step. This limitation is typically imposed by the presence of small elements, such as junctions, which often result in a time step that is disproportionately smaller than the time step in the EPA SWMM model for the same system. While this smaller time step can be a limitation, it can be effectively addressed through the use of parallel computing, which alleviates the computational burden (Hodges et al., 2024).

2.3 Comparison to Observed Data

Although the SWMM5+ simulation configuration and forcing in this study are directly adopted from the NWM setup without specific hydrodynamic tailoring (i.e., the model is *uncalibrated*), it is still valuable to include a preliminary comparison to observed data. Figure 5 shows the discharge timeseries results for SWMM5+ compared against USGS gauge data for two junctions in the Lavaca river network (seen in Fig. 1).

The results demonstrate that SWMM5+ can produce reasonable consistency with field observations, capturing comparable peak values and peak arrival times. The simplified configuration of trapezoidal bathymetry inherited from NWM may have lead to overestimates of discharge in the simulations. Nonetheless, as the primary objective of this study is to assess the performance of the SWMM5+ model relative to SPRNT and EPA SWMM, the simplified bathymetry assumption was retained to ensure convergence across all models and maintain consistent comparison standards.

Fig. 5. Comparison of SWMM5+ simulation results with field-observed daily discharge data from two gauges in the Lavaca River network. Left panel: USGS 08164450 (i.e., Star (1) in Fig. 1); right panel: USGS 08164503 (i.e., Star (2) in Fig. 1).

3 Initialize SVE Simulation – “Spin-Up Time”

The amount of time before simulated results are free from the impacts of uncertain initial conditions is commonly referred to as the model “spin-up time”. In numerical simulation, the spin-up time is generally unavoidable, as it is rarely possible to obtain precisely accurate spatially distributed initial conditions that are fully consistent with the corresponding spatially distributed boundary conditions at $t = 0$. As highlighted by Yu et al. (2017), no universal criterion exists for defining spin-up time in river network simulations; rather, it is influenced by the quality of initial condition configurations and the degree of consistency between initial and boundary conditions.

Herein the Lavaca and San Jacinto river basins were “spun-up” using slightly variable approaches. For the Lavaca River, relatively stable boundary conditions were imposed; for the San Jacinto River, real forcing data, including a significant runoff event, were utilized to evaluate model responses under dynamic hydrological conditions. Zero initial conditions were applied in the SWMM5+ and EPA SWMM models to assess their convergence to the SPRNT model, with the duration defined as the spin-up time. Convergence was determined based on the percentage difference between simulated hydrographs at the final junction upstream of the outlet, considering them converged when the difference remained within $\pm 1\%$ for a minimum period of six hours. The resulting discharge hydrographs and percentage differences between the models and the benchmark SPRNT model are presented in Figure 6.

Fig. 6. Spin-up analysis for the Lavaca and San Jacinto River networks using SWMM5+, EPA_{kin}, and EPA_{dyn}. Hydrographs are evaluated at the final junction upstream of the outlet for both river networks. The top panels depict the time required for hydrographs from each model to achieve convergence with the benchmark model, SPRNT. The bottom panels present the percentage differences between the three models and SPRNT over the simulation period.

The time a system takes to erase any memory of the initial conditions is largely a physical process, rather than a numerical one. Larger, shallower systems require more spin-up time than smaller, steeper ones. The results of Fig. 6 show that the discharge from the outfall of each comparison model converged to the SPRNT model within 350 hours for the Lavaca River, 200 hours for the San Jacinto River. Notably, the SWMM5+ model took the longest to converge for the Lavaca River with consistent boundary conditions, despite being the first to converge for the San Jacinto river with hydrologically realistic boundary conditions.

4 Postprocessing Techniques for Model-to-Model Analysis

4.1 Hydrograph Smoothing

Jagged, discontinuous behavior of solution variables presents an impediment to automated processing of hydrograph and stage results. To address this issue, our analysis workflow employs a non-linear median filter (NLMF) for smoothing noisy timeseries data, similar to the approach of White and Hodges (2005) for smoothing bathymetric data. The behavior of the NLMF is similar to a traditional moving-average window, except the use of the median value rather than the arithmetic average reduces the bias from spurious hydrograph spikes.

NLMF smoothing can be represented for a filter window of size $2N_f + 1$ as

$$\tilde{\phi}[x_i, t_k] = \text{MEDIAN}(\phi[x_i, t_{k-N_f}], \phi[x_i, t_{k-N_f+1}], \dots, \phi[x_i, t_{k+N_f}]) \quad (1)$$

where $\tilde{\phi}$ represents the NLMF-filtered data set. Values for $\phi[x_i, t_k < T_{\text{start}}]$ and $\phi[x_i, t_k > T_{\text{end}}]$ are ignored. The NLMF preserves key hydrograph features such as the slope of the rising limb and timing of peak flows.

Note: The magnitude of the peak is necessarily *lower* after the NLMF has been applied; once the peak has been identified, the raw data corresponding to the peak time is considered ϕ_p .

4.2 Extracting Baseflow to Identify Major Event Peaks

Continuous simulation of a regional-scale river network has, by definition, an extensive spatial and temporal domain. As such, the downstream reaches may show minor peaks as a result of localized hydrological events. Major events during the simulation window were identified as instances where the flow and stage exceeded the 75th percentile for that model.

From Fig. 5, four major events occurred during the five-month simulation period that generated discharge exceeding the 75th percentile for the SWMM5+ simulation. These events occurred on:

- Jan 20th, 2017
- Feb 21th, 2017
- Mar 6th, 2017
- Apr 19th, 2017

4.3 Sampling in Time & Space

In traditional model-to-observation comparisons, the resolution of the observational data drives the acceptable resolution for the comparative analysis. River gauge observational data often are available at a high time-resolution, but are limited to select locations spatially. In contrast, the model-model comparison study supported herein does not compare to gauged data but rather to the other models. As such, the behavior of the models can be compared at a variety of locations across the test cases. The improved spatial resolution of hydrograph and stage data strikes at a key advantage of model-to-model comparisons – model behavior can be correlated with the location of the sampling point within the system. E.g. the dissipation of a flood wave can be observed as it propagates through the network.

4.3.1 Time

The resolution of the forcing data was one hour (the resolution of hydrological inflow data derived from the post-calibrated NWM; David et al., 2011). The simulation reporting time resolution, then, was also set to one hour. A simulation time resolution of one hour is adequate for continuous simulation of regional-scale river networks that have undergone extensive simplifications (i.e. removal of dams/reservoirs, trapezoidal channel approximations).

However, the relatively granular time-resolution for model output has an exaggerated impact on sampling locations in the far upstream portions of each river network. In these locations, the concentration time for inflow pulses is less than the reporting resolution, resulting in step-function hydrographs. Further downstream, where the time of concentration is much greater than one hour, the simulated hydrographs and stage curves are much smoother. Figure 7(b) features flowrate hydrographs for two locations in the San Jacinto river network (locations shown in Fig. 1). Figure 7(a) depicts a peripheral reach hydrograph whose time of concentration is less than the one hour time-resolution, resulting in flood peaks with no rising or falling limbs. Whereas, figure 7(b) depicts the hydrograph of a main-stem channel near the system outfall. Here, flood wave dissipation and convolution combine to produce well-defined rising and falling limbs.

The constraint on the time-resolution for the present study has the effect of limiting the analysis to channels where the shape of the flood waves is identifiable. Effectively, this limits our analysis to channels belonging to Strahler order 4 and above.

(a) Hydrograph of Upstream Branch

(b) Hydrograph of Downstream Branch

Fig. 7. Hydrographs from the San Jacinto river network: a) Star (3) in Fig. 1, an upstream branch where the time of concentration is less than the time-resolution, and b) Star (4) in Fig. 1, a downstream branch where flood peaks are represented more fully.

4.3.2 Space

River reach junctions, i.e. locations in the system where two or more reaches converge, are a common instance where modeling approaches can differ substantially between simulation programs. The sampling locations for our model-to-model comparison were chosen to be directly downstream of network junctions. Sampling in these areas, it was reasoned, captures the model-to-model variance in handling flow through junctions, as well as preserves the differences in channelized flow-routing that accumulate in the reaches upstream of the junction.

Differences in the governing equations and discretization schemes for our comparison models dictate which solution variables are available at each network object. Figure 3 illustrated this difference in the context of creating EPA SWMM junctions from the SPRNT junction complex. In SPRNT’s finite-difference method, results for flowrate and head are available at *nodes*. In SWMM5+’s related finite-volume method, data for flowrate and head are available at *elements*, which formally border the nodes derived from SPRNT. Separately, in EPA SWMM’s conduit-node approach, flowrate is only available in *conduits*, while head is only available at *nodes*.

In this study, the sampling locations were set in SPRNT as the first node downstream of a junction confluence. Sampling locations were chosen in SWMM and SWMM5+ such that the necessary data was pulled from the nearest appropriate downstream network object. Distortion introduced by sampling data from neighboring network objects for each modeling paradigm is not expected to impact the results. The segment/element/conduit length was set to around 150 *m* in the model build phase, which, coupled with the one hour reporting resolution, is coarse enough that discrepancies due to sampling point difference should not appear.

The number of qualifying, junction-adjacent sampling locations for the Lavaca and San Jacinto river basins was 67 and 116, respectively.

4.4 Hydrograph agreement metrics

Five metrics are employed for the model-to-model comparison: Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency (NSE), Averaged Peak Magnitude Difference (AP_m), Averaged Peak Time Difference (AP_t), Temporal Series Distance (SD_t), and Amplitude Series Distance (SD_a). These metrics were computed from model hydrograph results using the formulas in Table 2 for sampling points at the downstream side of each junction. A single NSE value reflects all the temporal data over the simulation time (N_{time} data points) from the hydrograph at a sampling

point. Individual AP_m and AP_t values are computed over M major event peaks in the hydrograph over all simulation time at a sampling point. The SD_t and SD_a are computed for each major event and sampling point, then averaged.

Table 2. Analysis metrics where Q is flow rate with \bar{Q} as a time average, P is the peak magnitude of the hydrograph, t is the time of the hydrograph peak. Superscript b is for benchmark model (SPRNT) and superscript s is for comparison model (SWMM5+, EPA_{dyn}, EPA_{kin}). M is the number of identified major event peaks, and N denotes the total number of time steps over the comparing period.

metric	symbol	equation
Nash-Sutcliffe Efficiency	NSE	$1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q^b[i] - Q^s[i])^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (Q^b[i] - \bar{Q}^b)^2}$
Averaged Peak Magnitude Difference	AP_m	$\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \frac{P^s[i] - P^b[i]}{P^b[i]}$
Averaged Peak Time Difference	AP_t	$\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M (t^s[i] - t^b[i])$
Temporal Series Distance	SD_t	$\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \text{Dist}_t[i] $
Amplitude Series Distance	SD_a	$\frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \text{Dist}_a[i] $

The key distinction between the Averaged Peak (AP) metrics and the Series Distance (SD) metric lies in their respective analytical scopes. While the AP metrics summarize differences solely in terms of peak magnitude and peak timing between two hydrographs, the SD metric offers a more comprehensive comparison by averaging discrepancies over the entire duration of an event. This is achieved through pairwise matching of data points around peaks in the two model hydrographs, as illustrated in Figure 8 (Ehret & Zehe, 2011). The SD metric thereby captures both the average amplitude deviation and temporal displacement for each individual event, enabling finer-resolution evaluation of model performance. However, a potential drawback of the SD approach is the substantial volume of output it generates—specifically, N sampling locations each producing SD values for all M simulated events. This proliferation of data may not necessarily yield proportional analytical insight. Therefore, in this study, the application of the SD metric is constrained to three representative events per river basin to ensure focused and interpretable results.

Fig. 8. Illustration of pair-matching for temporal series distance (SD_t , subfigure a) and amplitude series distance (SD_v , subfigure b) illustrating a benchmark event (black) and a comparison event (grey). This figure extracted and reproduced from insets of Figs. 6 and 9 of Ehret and Zehe (2011).

5 Supplemental results from SVE simulation

The simulation results shown highlight the event-based peak discharge and the cumulative volume agreement between the comparison and baseline models at key locations within the study area. However, model-to-model comparisons of regional-scale river networks produce a spatially dense comparison matrix that is cumbersome to represent in a comprehensive way. Figure 9 shows the peak discharge and depth at each sampling location within the Lavaca River Network for each of the four major events identified in the methodology, as simulated by SWMM5+.

Fig. 9. SWMM5+ simulation results of peak discharge and depth for major events in the Lavaca River Network between January and June, 2017

Variability in precipitation patterns and intensities across a river network can result in notable differences in the shape and timing of hydrograph responses across events. To investigate these effects, three representative hydrological events were selected from each river basin to compute the series-based timing difference (SD_t) and magnitude difference (SD_v). For the Lavaca River, events on January 20, February 21, and April 19, 2017, were analyzed. For the San Jacinto River, the selected events occurred on January 20, February 21, and May 15, 2017. Figures 10 and 11 present the results for each basin, where SD_t is plotted against SD_v . Distinct markers are used to denote each hydrological event, and accompanying box plots along the top and right margins of each figure summarize the distributions of SD_t and SD_v across all sampling points. Analysis of the scatterplot in Figure 10 reveals that the SWMM5+ model consistently outperforms both the EPA_{kin} and EPA_{dyn} models across all three hydrological events examined. Specifically, the interquartile ranges of both SD_t and SD_v for SWMM5+ are markedly narrower, indicating more consistent temporal

and volumetric agreement with the reference simulation. The mean series difference values for SWMM5+ are $SD_v = 3.61 m^3/s$ and $SD_t = 2.73$ hours. For both EPA-based models, the SD_v values generally remain below $60 m^3/s$; however, two outliers exceeding $80 m^3/s$ are observed in the EPA_{dyn} model during the April 13 event. Upon manual inspection, these anomalous values were found to originate from two consecutive downstream locations and are attributable to numerical oscillations that were not fully mitigated by the post-processing smoothing procedures. In terms of SD_t , the EPA_{kin} model exhibits substantially higher timing discrepancies relative to SWMM5+ and EPA_{dyn}, particularly in downstream segments of the network across all events, underscoring its limited capability to accurately capture flood wave propagation timing.

Fig. 10. Scatter plot of timing series difference (SD_t) versus magnitude series difference (SD_v) for the Lavaca River, based on three hydrological events (January 20, February 21, and April 19, 2017). Box plots of SD_t and SD_v are included along the top and right margins, respectively, to illustrate the distribution of timing and magnitude differences for each model.

Similar patterns are found in the distribution of SD_t and SD_v in San Jacinto River network in Figure 11. The SWMM5+ model demonstrates notably better performance among the three models, characterized by a narrower range of SD_t and SD_v . Additionally, it is noteworthy that the EPA_{dyn} model exhibits

a similar tendency to produce excessive SD_v values in downstream channels, attributable to oscillatory numerical results, as we observed in the Lavaca River case. From the author's observation, the EPA_{dyn} simulations exhibit more pronounced numerical instability in the San Jacinto River compared to the Lavaca River. Despite the application of a moving average filter to mitigate fluctuations, the filter is insufficient to address the severe oscillations, particularly in downstream channels where the numerical instability is most pronounced. For comparison and demonstration purposes, these samples are retained in the scatter plot. The EPA_{kin} continues to exhibit similar behavior to what was observed in the Lavaca case, with a comparable level of SD_v to the SWMM5+ model but a broader range of SD_t , particularly in channels near the river outlet.

Fig. 11. Scatter plot of timing series difference (SD_t) versus magnitude series difference (SD_v) for the San Jacinto River, based on three hydrological events (January 20, February 21, and May 16, 2017). Box plots of SD_t and SD_v are included along the top and right margins, respectively, to illustrate the distribution of timing and magnitude differences for each model.

6 Adjustments and configurations made in the solvers to ensure the acquirement of comparable results

To preserve the full dynamics of the Saint-Venant governing equations, a specific code block in the Dynamic Wave module (`dwflow.c`) of the SWMM5 source code was commented out, following guidance from Rossman, Dickinson, and Tiernan (2022). Figure 13 illustrates the simulated flow rate at the outfall of the Lavaca River network over the first 40 days of simulation using the EPA_{dyn} solver, under two configurations: (a) with the normal flow limitation removed to enable full hydrodynamic complexity, and (b) with the default normal flow limitation enabled. The results demonstrate that disabling the normal flow limiter improves numerical stability at the network outlet. Accordingly, all EPA_{dyn} simulations in this study were conducted with the normal flow limitation disabled to ensure consistent application of the complete Saint-Venant equations.

```
// --- check for normal flow limitation based on surface slope & Fr
else
if ( y1 < Link[j].xsect.yFull &&
    ( Link[j].flowClass == SUBCRITICAL ||
      Link[j].flowClass == SUPCRITICAL )
    ) q = checkNormalFlow(j, q, y1, y2, a1, r1);
```

Fig. 12. Screenshot of normal flow limiting code block in `dwflow.c`. When the block is activated, a normal flow condition is enforced.

(a) Default normal flow limiter deactivated.

(b) Default normal flow limiter activated.

Fig. 13. Simulated flowrates at the outfall of the Lavaca River Network from EPA_{dyn} showing stability difference from toggling the normal flow limiting code block in the `dwflow.c` module.

7 Conclusion

This technical report provides supporting documentation for the journal article “Advancing Watershed-Scale Hydrodynamic Modeling with the Saint-Venant Equations”, with a focus on the implementation details, adjustments, and supplemental analyses used in the model-to-model comparison. The material presented here includes practical steps for constructing large-scale river network models, setting up numerical experiments using Saint-Venant solvers, and post-processing methods for evaluating flood wave behavior.

This report outlines the procedures used to generate regional-scale river network models for the Lavaca and San Jacinto River basins, including simplifications applied to channel geometry, node inflow handling, and bathymetric assumptions. It also describes modifications made to the SWMM5 source code to preserve full hydrodynamic dynamics, as well as the rationale for including each solver in the comparison.

The post-processing methods detailed in this report—such as event-based series distance metrics and spatial error mapping—serve as practical tools for diagnosing numerical behavior across complex river systems. In addition, supplemental results are provided to illustrate model differences in hydrograph shape, flood wave timing, and numerical stability under identical forcing.

Overall, this report is intended to enhance the transparency and reproducibility of the modeling workflow described in the main article. It also serves as a reference for researchers seeking to apply or extend the comparison framework to additional river systems or solvers. By documenting implementation-specific choices and solver configurations, we hope this resource supports continued development and evaluation of watershed-scale hydrodynamic models using the Saint-Venant equations.

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